

**THE EFFECT OF AMBON BANANA STEM EXTRACT (*MUSA PARADISIACA*
VAR. SAPIENTUM) AGAINST TUMOR NECROSIS FACTOR ALPHA
EXPRESSION (TNF- α) ON GASTRIC OF RATS (*RATTUS NORVEGICUS*)
INDUCTED BY INDOMETHACIN**

N R Pramestya, R Kurnijasanti¹, Soeharsono¹, Suwarno¹

¹ University of Airlangga, Surabaya, East Java, Indonesia

nindarubi@yahoo.com

Abstract

The purpose of this research was to prove the role of ambon banana stem (*Musa paradisiaca* var. *sapientum*) against inflammation as measured by decreased expression of Tumor Necrosis Factor Alpha (TNF- α) in gastric of rat (*Rattus norvegicus*). Twenty rats (*Rattus norvegicus*) with 8-12 week ages and 150-200 g average of body weight were divided into five groups (K-, K+, P1, P2 and P3). K- and K+ as control, P1 was treated with ambon banana stem extract dose 200mg/kg BW, P2 was treated with ambon banana stem extract dose 400mg/kg BW, P3 was treated with ambon banana stem extract dose 800/kg BW. This research has been conducted for 13 days. The data of TNF- α expression were analyzed with Kruskal-Wallis and continued with Man-Whitney. Result showed there were significant ($p < 0.05$) different between treatment groups. This research conclude that ambon banana stem extract with dose 800mg/kg BW can prevent gastritis on gastric of rats.

DOI : 10.5281/zenodo.2582244

1.Introduction

Gastritis is an inflammatory process in the mucosa and submucosa of the stomach caused by irritation and infection factors. Gastritis is one of the most common health problems of the digestive tract. The percentage of incidence of gastritis in Indonesia by World Health Organization (WHO) (2010) is 40.8% of the population per year and the incidence of gastritis in some areas in Indonesia is quite high with the prevalence of 274,396 cases of 238,452,952 in 2004 (Hirlan, 2009 and Gustin, 2012).Gastritis caused by alcohol consumption, microorganisms, acute stress, radiation or intoxication of food and beverage, bile salts, direct traumatic, and use of Non Steroid Anti-inflammatory Drugs (NSAID), such as Indomethacin, Ibuprofen, and Salicylic Acid with continuous consumption and excessive dosage (Muttaqin and Kumala, 2011 and Sagall, 2006).

Indonesia is a tropical country, therefore it is possible plants can grow, primarily medicinal plants. Utilization of medicinal plants can be used as an alternative to fulfill basic needs in the health sector, especially in remote areas that difficulty to get conventional medicine. Medicinal plants are easy plants obtained, known by many people, the process of storage is simple, easy

used and harmless to its users (Muktiningsih *et. al.*, 2001). One of the medicinal plants is banana plant. Banana plants were first found and thrives in tropical regions of the developing world such as Indi china and Southeast Asia (Satuhu and Supriyadi, 2008). One of the banana plants that thrives in the tropics is Ambon Banana plant (*Musa paradisiaca var sapientum*) (Suyanti and Supriyadi, 2008).

Ambon Banana Plant (*Musa paradisiaca var sapientum*) is one of the medical plant that has many benefits because almost all parts of plant starting from the stem, leaves, flowers and fruit can be utilized. Banana stem has phytochemical content consisting of tannins, saponins, and flavonoids that have antioxidant and anti-inflammatory effects that can directly function to neutralize the effects toxic from free radicals and can stimulate the growth of new cells in the wound, in addition to vitamin A and vitamin C, fat and protein that can help the wound healing process (Priosoeryanto *et. al.*, 2006). In Prayoga research (2016) proved that Ambon banana extract is effective to cure Inflammatory Bowel Disease in rats.

Based on the background, it is necessary to study The effect of Ambon banana stem extract (*Musa paradisiaca var. sapientum*) against tumor necrosis factor alpha expression (TNF- α) on gastric of rats (*Rattus norvegicus*) induced by Indomethacin.

2.Experimental Methods

This research was conducted in June 2017. Animal research and treatment was conducted at Try Animal Unit of Faculty of Veterinary Medicine of Airlangga University. The process of making Ambon banana extraction was implemented at Veterinary Department of Basic medical veterinary science of Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, Airlangga University. The preparation of histopathology preparations was implemented at Pathology Laboratory of Veterinary Faculty of Airlangga University. Immunohistochemistry staining was implemented at Anatomy Pathology Laboratory of Faculty of Medicine Brawijaya University. A total of 20 male rats (*Rattus norvegicus*) of wistar strains were used as research objects that have passed the ethical test. White rats age 8-12 weeks weighing 150-200 grams. During maintenance, rats were fed and drank in ad libitum.

The tools used in the research are: rat cage, wood powder for pedestal base, drinking bottle, feeding place. Equipment for making histopathology and immunohistochemistry: Surgical set (scissors, scalpels, tweezers and surgical boards), gloves, object glass, glass cover, small pots for organ storage, paper labels, water bath. Equipment for extraction (digital scales, stirring rod, rotary vacuum evaporator, tissue, cotton, erlenmeyer, measuring cu), microscope, peroral injection.

The materials used in the research are: Ambon banana stem, 96% ethanol, sterile aquadest, CMC Na 0.5%, Indomethacin ($C_{19}H_{16}ClNO_4$) (Sigma Aldrich), corn oil, mouse feed (chicken pellet), mineral water. Preparation materials include gastric tissue, 10% formaldehyde buffer, 70% ethanol, 80%, 90%, 96%, 0.9% physiological salt (NaCl), paraffin, transparent adhesive, xylol, Phosphat Buffered Saline (PBS), H_2O_2 , Bovine Serum Albumin (BSA), primary

antibodies (TNF- α), secondary antibodies, DAB chromogen solution (3,3-diaminobenzidine tetrahydrochloride), eosin hematoxylin.

This research uses Completely Randomized Design. The number of samples used in this study is based on the federer's repetition formula.

The process of extracting the Ambon banana stem was using maceration method. Simplicia was immersed in 96% ethanol for 4 days, than filtered using filter paper and the filtrate was evaporated up by rotary vacuum evaporator in temperature between 40 ° C-50° C and speed 40 rpm until obtained by thick extract (Iswani, 2007).

This study consisted of 5 types of treatment with 4 replications per treatment. K-was a rat given CMC Na 0.5% with a dose of 0.5ml / 150g of rat BW / per oral for 7 days. On the 8th day, CMC Na 0,5% was given. An hour later was given corn oil with a dose of 0.5ml / 150g of rat WB / per oral. On the 9th day, CMC Na 0,5% is given again until 12th day. K + was a rat given CMC Na 0.5% a dose of 0.5ml / rat /per oral / day for 7 days. On the 8th day, CMC Na 0,5% was given. One hour later was given Indomethacin with a dose of 2,25mg / 0,5ml emulsion of corn oil / 150g of rat WB / per oral. On the 9th day, CMC Na was given again until 12th. P1 was a rat given Ambon banana stem extract which was dissolved with CMC Na0,5% with dose 200mg / 0,5ml/ kg BW for 7 days. On the 8th day, a Ambon banana stem extract which was dissolved with CMC Na 0.5%. One hour later was given Indomethacin emulsion 2.25 mg / 0,5ml corn oil / 150 g BB / per oral and 9th day was given banana extract of Ambon banana again until 12th day. P2 was the rats given the same treatment as P1 but with dose of Ambon banana extract is 400 mg / kg body weight / oral and P3 dose 800 mg / kg body weight.

Each field of view was observed positive TNF- α expression, then in percentage with score from 0 to 4. The number 0 had a percentage level of positive TNF- α expression 0, number 1 percentage level of positive TNF- α expression <10%, number 2 percentage level positive TNF- α expression of 11-50%, the rate of 3 levels of TNF- α expression positive percentage of 51-80%, the rate of 4 levels the percentage of positive TNF- α expression is more than 80%. Figures 0-2 include low expression categories, 3 expression category numbers and 4 high expression categories. Median scores were the median mean score (Nowak *et al.*, 2007).

3.Result And Discussion

Results of histopathologic examination of rat stomach with immunohistochemistry staining were examined under a microscope with magnification 400 times to see the expression of Tumor Necrosis Factor Alpha (TNF- α). The expression of Tumor Necrosis Factor Alpha (TNF- α) in the rat gastic tissue was visualized with brownish color.

The brown color is the result of a reaction between antigens that bind to primary antibodies TNF- α and secondary antibodies as well as diamino benzidine (DAB) substrates. Tissue that does not express Tumor Necrosis Factor Alpha (TNF- α) will be blue. In the negative control (K-) seen

TNF- α is visualized with brownish color in the gland part but the blue color is still very dominating.

Positive control (K +) shows a TNF- α expression visualized by a dominant brown color in the glandular portion. P 1 is still seen as TNF- α is visualized with a brownish color in the glandular portion. P 2 is still present in TNF- α is visualized with brownish color in the gland section but less than P 1, whereas P 3 appears to be TNF- α is visualized with brownish color in the gland section but has not dominated. Expression of Tumor Necrosis Factor Alpha (TNF- α) in the histology of the gastric tissue of white rats can be seen in (Figure 1)

Figure 1. Expression of Tumor Necrosis Factor Alpha (TNF- α) Group K +, P1, P2, P3 in the gland (400x magnification, Immunohistochemistry staining. Positive TNF- α expression is shown yellow arrow, negative TNF- α expression is indicated by a red arrow.

The histopathologic picture of the K- , gland group expresses TNF- α with little intensity. This is due to outside variables that can not be controlled such as feeding that is less in accordance with the standard, less ideal cage conditions, stress factors during the study took place, as well as the beginning of stomach conditions unhealthy rat. In the K + group rats were given indomethacin as a gastritis model without being given the extract of the banana ambon as the therapy. Indomethacin works by inhibiting COX-1 and reducing the cytoprotective effect of prostaglandins that can lead to the side effect of gastritis. Indicators of gastritis one of them is TNF- α expression on immunohistochemistry staining with brown color as a positive reaction. This brownish color appears due to the reaction between the antigen binding to the primary antibody K-K + P1 P2 P3 TNF- α and secondary antibodies as well as diaminobenzidine substrate (DAB). TNF- α is derived from mononuclear phagocyte cells and the other source is T cells stimulated by active NK cells and active mast cells. The source is derived from the blood vessels in the connective tissue which then recognize lesion resulting chemotaxis process where the phagocyte cells out of the blood vessels to the tissue through the glandular channel, so that histopathologic picture appears brownish color in the gastric gland as an indicator of the number

of inflammatory cells (Mok and Kwan , 2002 and Abbas *et al.*, 2010). This study is in line with research Anggaini *et al.* (2013) which states that the side effects of indomethacin is gastritis.

Based on the result of the analysis test on P1 group significantly different with K-, P2 and P3 but not significantly different with K +, this shows that banana Ambon stem extract at dose 200 mg / kg BW less effective to prevent gastritis. Group P2 was not significantly different with P3 but was significantly different from K-, K + and P1, it showed that banana Ambon stem extract at 400 mg / kg BW was still less effective to prevent gastritis. P3 group is not significantly different with K- and P2 but the real difference with P1, K +, means that extract of banana Ambon stem at dose 800 mg / kg BW is the optimal dose to prevent gastritis. Flavonoid substances in the extract of banana Ambon stem serves as an antioxidant and anti-inflammatory. As antioxidants directly act to neutralize the toxic effects of free radicals by giving hydrogen atoms from their clusters to react with free radicals to become stable compounds. The loss of free radicals can inhibit the activity of T cells resulting in the substance of inflammation proteins are not activated so that blood vessels do not experience dilatation and edema does not occur. The flavonoid as anti-inflammatory agent works by inhibiting T cell activation (helper 1 T cells). Barriers to T helper 1 cells cause Tumor Necrosis Factor Alpha (TNF- α) inactivation. TNF- α inactivation leads to a decrease in the presence of neutrophils, leading to tissue repair and a decrease in inflammatory cells (Zhang, 2005). This study is in line with that examined by Prayoga (2016) which states that the extract of banana Ambon stem can be used as anti-inflammatory drugs.

4. Conclusion

Based on the results of this study, it can be concluded that giving extract of banana Ambon stem (*Musa paradisiaca var. sapientum*) has an effect on decreasing expression of Tumor Necrosis Factor Alpha (TNF- α) in white rat's stomach (*Rattus norvegicus*) at dose 800 mg / kg BB rat.

REFERENCE

- [1] Abbas, A., Lichtman, A., and Pillai, S. 2010, *Celullar and Molecular Immunology*, 6th Ed. Philadelphia: W.B Saunders Company.
- [2] Anggraini, D. I., Pudjono and Albert, Y., 2013, *Sintesis Isopropil Indometasin Dari Indometasinil Klorida Dengan Isopropil Alkohol*. Jurnal Ilmiah Kesehatan V, (5):2. 1
- [3] Gustin, Rahmi Kurnia, 2012, *Faktor – Faktor yang Berhubungan dengan Kejadian Gastritis pada Pasien yang Berobat Jalan di Puskesmas Gulai Boncah Kota Bukit Tinggi Tahun.2011*, Bukit Tinggi.
- [4] Hirlan, 2009, *Gastritis dalam Ilmu Penyakit Dalam*, Jilid I Edisi V. Jakarta: InternaPublishing.

- [5] Iswani, S. 2007, *Proses Preparasi Ekstrak Kasar Etanol dari Makrolaga untuk Uji Farmakologi*. 3-5.
- [6] Muttaqin, Arif & Sari, Kumala, 2011, *Gangguan Gastrointestinal: Aplikasi Asuhan Keperawatan Medikal bedah*. Jakarta: Salemba medika.
- [7] Mok, C., and Kwan, J, 2002, *Tolerability of aspirin and predictors for withdrawal in elderly patients*. JHK Geriatr Soc , 11: 6-12.
- [8] Priosoeryanto, B., H, Huminto, I, Wientarsih, dan S, Estuningsih, 2006, *Aktifitas Getah Batang Pohon Pisang dalam Proses Persembuhan Luka dan Efek Kosmetikny pada Hewan*. Lembaga Penelitian dan Pemberdayaan Masyarakat IPB, 3, Bogor
- [9] Prayoga, R. D, 2016, *Pengaruh Ekstrak Batang Pisang Ambon (Musa paradisiaca var. sapientum) Terhadap Gambaran Histopatologi Jejunum Tikus (Rattus norvegicus) Inflammatory Bowel Disease*. Surabaya: Universitas Airlangga.
- [10] Satuhu, S., dan Supriyadi, A, 2008, *Pisang: Budidaya, Pengolahan, dan Prospek*. Jakarta: Penebar Swadaya.
- [11] Sagall, RJ, 2006 *Ibuprofen and stomach ulcers*. Pediatrics for parents journals, vol 22,5; p 1-22. Academic Research library.

